

COMPETENCY APPROACH AS A MODERN COMPUTER TEACHING PARADIGM

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Abstract. *In order to comprehensively solve the task of preparing young people for real professional and life activities, it is necessary to develop and put into practice the state educational standards and curricula based on the competence approach for general education subjects that are taught organically in general secondary education. This article discusses this.*

Keywords: *competence approach, computer education, educational system.*

In order to comprehensively solve the task of preparing young people for real professional and life activities, it is necessary to develop and put into practice the state educational standards and curricula based on the competence approach for general education subjects that are taught organically in general secondary education. Taking these aspects into account, the task of introducing a principled new methodology of teaching academic subjects at all stages of general compulsory education was defined.

As a result of the above-mentioned social needs, as a paradigm of modern education in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to develop the scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of education based on the competence approach, and general education is aimed at forming the ability to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in their personal, professional and social activities. The basics of compensatory education were gradually introduced [1]. "The social and emotional component plays an important role in successful pedagogy" in the manual "Analysis of policies regulating the field of preparation, publication and use of textbooks in Uzbekistan" jointly with the Ministry of Public Education and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) [2].

Lessons are social, and the learning goal is both social and academic. The emotional aspect is also important in stimulating students' interest in reading. "Textbooks provide ample opportunities for teachers to ensure that students not only acquire practical knowledge, but also develop the skills of interpretation, thinking, emotional impact, effective communication and creativity" [2. p.15] should help. Such an approach required clarifying the structure, components, criteria and indicators of the development of communicative competence in students of general secondary school, improving the model of development of communicative competence in students and didactic support.

Robert Oker "We should teach children how to think, not what to do. Our task is not only to give knowledge, but also to teach them wisdom. Intelligence is not only a set of knowledge, but also its effective use. In this regard, children should not be forced to explore the world and search for the truth from their point of view. Improvement of imagination, formation of conscientiousness and responsibility, education based on love - one of the main issues of the 21st century education system. In general, this is the essence of humanity in the future," he says [3].

At the international congress on education held at the end of the last century, pedagogue scientist Jacques Delorf in his lecture entitled "Education is a hidden treasure" described four aspects on which education is based: learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together, learning to live. [4]. According to him, learning to perform means not only having professional competence, but also being competent in a broad sense, being able to work in groups and successfully overcome many complex situations that arise during work.

The English scientist John Carlyle Raven created the foundations of competence by citing a "list of socially effective behavioral characteristics" of a person. According to his concept, the educational process of the general education system should be comprehensively oriented to the knowledge, social mobility, economic and cultural adaptation of students. "In order for public schools to be able to provide excellent education, it is necessary to create these opportunities for their students, taking into account different values and freedom of choice" [5].

Russian scientist M.I. Rozhkov described the interdependence of socially flexible and existential-developing approaches in the technology of educating a socially active person as follows: educating the need to be a person; formation of social maturity and readiness for active activity in market conditions; building immunity against the negative effects of the environment; educating a person in action, ready to show himself personally in various spheres of socially useful and important activity [6]. According to the research of M.I. Rozhkov, the subject of social activity is "a rational person who seeks to maximize his benefit in the conditions of completeness of information and freedom of choice. It is characterized by: "subjective activity, competence, prudence, business acumen, willingness to take risks, being personally responsible for one's actions" [6].

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